

Assessment and Demonstration

Technical standards

Building integrated PV modules/systems, being at the same time generators of electricity and part of the building envelope, have to be compliant with both electro technical standards and existing building codes and practices. Standardization about BIPV systems is under discussion and progressing at international level in ongoing research activities and working groups. BIPV sector, within the legal framework set by the CPR 305/2011, can rely on a solid building normative framework and, for specific requirements, next researches and standardization works are going to contribute in covering gaps and support BIPV market with testing and performances assessment.

BIPV quality, standards, normative compliance, testing procedures, safety

target audience (Regulation makers / Owners & other decision makers / Architects & engineers / Suppliers & companies)

According to EN 50583, Parts 1 and 2, "Photovoltaics in buildings" [1], "Photovoltaic modules are considered to be building-integrated, if the PV modules form a construction product providing a function as defined in the European Construction Product Regulation CPR 305/2011 [2]. Thus, the BIPV module is a prerequisite for the integrity of the building's functionality. If the integrated PV module is dismantled (in the case of structurally bonded modules, dis-mounting includes the adjacent construction product), the PV module would have to be replaced by an appropriate construction product". But what beyond definitions? Which is the reality for the market?

In most of the EU countries, as well as in Switzerland, there are not harmonized BIPV standards for the building skin technologies (e.g. curtain walls, cold façades, etc..) or official regulations defining special technical requirements and testing/qualification procedures for building envelopes integrating PV. From the electro technical side, the design qualification and type approval of PV modules according to the standard EN 61215 or EN 61646 but they cannot provide a reliable performance assessment for most of the building requirements. On the other side, from the building perspective, In the current framework a BIPV system is often considered as the conventional equivalent system it is replacing, such as a curtain wall façade or a pitched roof. Thus, depending on the main mounting categories (roof, façade and external devices) and the main composing material (e.g. glass, membrane, metal, plastic, etc.), the essential BIPV requirements are defined, and the main reference performance are taken from existing standards for construction products. For example, if according to the type of installation PV components can be treated as glazing systems for the building skin, the construction rules of glass building skin are entitled to be met. Accordingly, some industries of BIPV glasses, thanks to the combination of extensive glass know-how with photovoltaic technology, mark their products according to CE-marking for laminated safety glasses - not developed for PV building integration. Once the requirements for the BIPV final intended use in the building skin are identified, the related building performances have to be verified, to assess if the element can be used or not in building envelope (e.g. mechanical safety, fire safety, glass safety, etc. -see the basic requirements for construction works are set out in Annex I of CPR 305/2011). Formally, if the EN 50583:2016 is applied, It is also necessary to obtain the correct qualification procedure for applying a CE-mark as a construction product according to CPR 305/2011.

Electrical

PV Module

- [IEC 61646: Thin-film terrestrial photovoltaic \(PV\) modules, Design qualification and type approval](#)
- [IEC 61215: Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic \(PV\) modules, Design qualification and type approval](#)
- [IEC 61730: Photovoltaic module safety qualification](#)
- [Low Voltage Directive \(LVD\) 2006/95/CE \(CE-marking of electrical devices\)](#)
- [Electromagnetic Compatibility Directive \(EMCD\)](#)

Building

Building product

- [Construction Products Regulation \(CPR\)](#)
 - Basic requirements for building products (Annex I)
 - General principles for CE-mark ([DoP](#), [hENs](#), [ETA](#), ...)
 - Harmonized Standards ([hENs](#)) and European technical Assessment ([ETA](#))

CE –Mark for Building products

In conclusion we can summarize that:

- BIPV elements, as part of the building construction, are affected by both European Directives for Construction Products and Electro-technical standards for PV products.
- Construction products must comply with harmonized standards where available, or the corresponding alternatives allowed by Construction Products Regulation.
- Further requirements on construction products are given by the national building codes
- In the case of composite material-based construction products such as BIPV, most current standards seem to be not directly applicable/valid for testing some technical requirements (e.g. mechanical, fire safety, etc.)

A performance-based methodology shall be applied for each BIPV project, because the required performances can vary depending on the BIPV project location, the building's geometry and typology, the use as well as the envelope system and the specific conventional PV module. Once clarified the final intended use in the building skin of the PV element, the standards in force (e.g. building codes) can be applied to BIPV elements to verify an adequate performance level for the building use (e.g. this is already adopted in many BIPV glasses for a performance assessment like the safety glass, mechanical resistance, g-value, U-value, etc.). However in most cases some missing gaps are still calling for further research since BIPV requirements cannot be considered the simple sum of building and PV prescriptions in force, so that the developments of new testing procedure for a performance-based approach is still a relevant question for BIPV sector [2][3].

Next challenge in BIPV field will be to identify missing gaps within the current standardization work and existing normative in relation to the most relevant BIPV requirements, performance risks, reliability and potential failure mechanisms to define which are the main routes for the development of new qualification procedures to support the market.

References

- [1] Regulation (EU) No 305/2011. European Construction Product Regulation
- [2] EN 50583:2016 Photovoltaics in Buildings (part 1: BIPV modules and part 2: BIPV system).
- [3] Bonomo, P., Frontini, F., Saretta, E., Caccivio, M. Bellenda, G., Manzini, G. Cappellano, P.G. (2017) Fire Safety of PV Modules and Buildings: Overviews, Bottlenecks and Hints, EU PVSEC 2017"
- [4] Saretta, E., Bonomo, P., Frontini, F. (2016). Laminated BIPV glass: approaches for the integration in the building skin. In Jens Schneider and Bernhard Weller (Eds.), Engineered Transparency 2016: Glass in Architecture and Structural Engineering (363-372). Ernst&Sohn.